

Project CHANGES - Spoke 5

D1.2 – Technical report on design of multimodal diagnostics

Deliverable information

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1	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CNR	Member, Leader
2	Opificio delle Pietre Dure	OPD	Member, co-leader
3	Università di Bologna	Uni Bo	Member
4	Università di Firenze	Uni Fi	Member
5	Università di Catania	Uni CT	Member
6	Gran Sasso Science Institute	GSSI	Member
7	Università La Sapienza	Uni RM1	Member
8	Edil Co.	EdilCO	Member

Executive Summary

This deliverable, *D1.2 – Technical Report on Design of Multimodal Diagnostics*, presents the design of novel instrumentation and methodologies within the CHANGES project, Work Package 1 (WP1) “Advanced Non-invasive Methods for Sustainable Diagnostics in Heritage Science”. WP1 seeks to innovate sustainable, non-invasive diagnostic instruments and analytical protocols tailored for the complex needs of cultural heritage preservation, aiming to advance the diagnostic capabilities essential for the conservation and study of historical artifacts.

WP1 integrates and harmonizes advanced instrumentation, combining various non-destructive analytical techniques—such as hyperspectral imaging (HSI), X-ray fluorescence (XRF) imaging, optical coherence tomography (OCT), X-ray computed tomography (CT), Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, a comprehensive research program designed to gather diverse and complementary data on the material composition and stratigraphy of tangible cultural heritage. By enhancing the depth and quality of information that can be obtained non-invasively, these methods facilitate a deeper understanding on multiple levels: raw materials, production technologies, and degradation processes. This knowledge is essential for developing evidence-based strategies for conservation and valorization.

The activities conducted under WP1 include:

- **Design and development of a combined XRF and CT imaging system:** the design and prototyping of a compact X-ray imaging system enable elemental mapping and 3D imaging of immovable artifacts directly within museum or site settings.
- **Design and development of a combined IR and XRF imaging device based on a cyber-physical collaborative cobot:** the development of combined an IR/XRF system where a measuring head is driven by a collaborative robotic arm allows the simultaneous acquisition

of elemental and molecular information at three-dimensional level and offers the possibility to visualize the compositional distribution on 3D artworks with a complex geometry.

- **Design and development of a combined OCT and HIS device:** the development of a combined OCT and HSI instrument allows simultaneous acquisition of tomographic and spectral datacubes, particularly useful in distinguishing varnish layers from underlying glazes and paints. This setup provides a non-invasive solution for studying both surface and subsurface features with micron-level precision.
- **Development of multimodal diagnostic protocols:** a) combination of FTIR, XRF, and Eddy Current (EC) measurements for the precise, non-invasive analysis of organic films on metal surfaces, with a specific utility in the monitoring of protective coatings over time to offer optimized conservation approaches; b) combination of HSI with Spatially Offset Raman Spectroscopy (SORS) to examine complex layered structures in mock-up paintings for non-destructive stratigraphic analysis and the distinction between different pigments and binders with high accuracy.

The collaborative and interdisciplinary framework of WP1 aims to develop innovative diagnostic tools that align with the sustainability goals of the CHANGES project. The designed technologies and protocols enhance both the accessibility and accuracy of heritage diagnostics, providing valuable methodologies applicable to a wide range of conservation scenarios.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Objectives

This deliverable, D1.2 – *Technical Report on Design of Multimodal Diagnostics*, outlines the research and development activities carried out by the institutions participating in Spoke 5 of the CHANGES project, specifically within Work Package 1 (WP1), titled *Advanced Non-invasive Methods for Sustainable Diagnostics in Heritage Science*. The main objective of WP1 is to address a critical need in the field of heritage diagnostics: developing high-performance, non-invasive technologies capable of delivering detailed insights into the material composition, structure, and stratigraphy of cultural heritage artifacts, while ensuring their full preservation.

The recent evolution of diagnostic tools has made it possible to move from bulky, lab-based systems to highly portable and versatile instruments suitable for in situ deployment. This has significantly expanded the range of possible applications, enabling more flexible diagnostics directly within museums, conservation workshops, or archaeological sites. In parallel, the integration of multiple, complementary techniques as the multimodal approach, has proven essential for the study of the complex, heterogeneous, and multilayered systems often encountered in historical artifacts.

Within this framework, WP1 has focused on selecting and combining a suite of analytical methods that have demonstrated high relevance and reliability in heritage science, including reflection-mode FTIR spectroscopy, XRF, optical coherence tomography (OCT), hyperspectral imaging (HSI) and X-ray tomography. These are being integrated into novel diagnostic platforms designed to address diverse conservation scenarios and to

improve the precision, depth, and interpretative power of non-invasive analyses.

1.2 State of the Art in Non-invasive Heritage Diagnostics

1. *Hyperspectral Imaging (HSI)*: This technique, which captures and analyzes a wide spectrum of wavelengths for each pixel, has become crucial in the non-destructive analysis of painted objects. Its ability to detect compositional differences that can be linked to different pigments or binders across the visible or near-infrared spectrum respectively, applied to a two-dimensional space, allows a detailed mapping of the materials. Recent advancements in HSI technology have improved spatial and spectral resolution, enabling the detection of alterations and retouching, as well as the identification of underlying compositions without damaging the original artwork [1-3]. Studies have shown the benefits of combining HSI with advanced multivariate statistics like principal component analysis (PCA), which can isolate specific spectral features and aid in reconstructing the stratigraphy of complex, multi-layered paintings. This makes HSI highly effective in distinguishing pigments with similar visual appearance but different chemical composition, enhancing its value in multimodal heritage diagnostics [4].

2. *IR Spectroscopy (IR)*: IR spectroscopy is widely used in heritage science for its ability to identify organic compounds, such as varnishes, oils, resins, and other binders, through their unique vibrational *pattern*. Its application in heritage diagnostics has been bolstered by the introduction of portable FTIR devices, which now allow for in situ analyses with high sensitivity [5, 6]. Advances in external reflection FTIR (ERS) have expanded FTIR's capability to detect even thin films and varnish layers. This is especially beneficial for understanding material stratigraphy, as FTIR can provide depth-resolved information when used in reflection modes [7]. When discrete chemical information from IR is

extended to chemical imaging, FTIR can reveal the distribution of organic materials across a surface, supporting the non-invasive mapping of materials in layered structures. High adaptability and growing portability have made FTIR spectroscopy an invaluable tool in multimodal setups, especially when assessing the preservation state of organic layers and monitoring conservation treatments [8].

3. *X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) Spectroscopy*: XRF is a well-established technique for elemental analysis, and its non-invasive nature makes it a popular choice in heritage science. Portable XRF spectrometers, with recent improvements in resolution and sensitivity, can now analyze lighter elements more accurately, expanding the range of materials and historical artifacts it can examine [9-12]. In recent years, developments in portable XRF devices have focused on miniaturization and enhanced sensitivity, with technologies like helium flushing to improve detection of low atomic number elements [13]. XRF is frequently used for identifying pigments and construction materials in artworks, providing essential data on composition, provenance, and conservation history.

4. *Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is a well-established technique for the non-invasive stratigraphy of transparent and turbid media, such as paint layers, varnishes, protective coatings, and patinas [14-18]. However, the technique performs poorly in the presence of highly scattering materials: as an example, Atkinson et al. highlighted the difficulties in distinguishing glaze layers on paintings (colored, translucent layers containing pigments with refractive indices very close to the binding medium) from those of aged varnish due to similarities in their scattering properties which gave similar appearance in OCT images [19]. The proposed hybrid OCT-hyperspectral imaging prototype is designed to address a key limitation of conventional OCT systems: the integration of spectral data is expected to be decisive in discriminating between materials with similar scattering*

properties.

5. X-ray radiography and tomography are widely employed in Cultural Heritage (CH) research, as demonstrated by numerous conservation projects. X-ray imaging techniques were initially applied to CH using medical CT scanners — a practice still common today. However, these systems provide accurate results only when analysing samples similar in size and density to the human body, a condition rarely met in CH studies with the exception of samples such as mummified remains. The importance of X-ray imaging techniques in Heritage Science is highlighted by their extensive use [20-27]. Tomography, in particular, may reveal detailed internal structures with remarkable detail, shedding light on manufacturing techniques of artworks or previous, often undocumented, conservation interventions, the presence of non-original materials and/or degradation products— all crucial elements for proper conservation planning or for a comprehensive knowledge of the object. In this context, transportable systems are of particular interest as they allow in-situ analysis, thus eliminating the risks related to the transport of artworks and artifacts [4, 6, 7, 8]. Particularly in the case of tomography, a widespread issue in conservation is the lack of portable/transportable equipment. In addition, open-source equipment is highly desirable as it ensures full customizability to meet specific user needs. The PNRR CHANGES project offered an excellent opportunity to address this gap, by responding to specific needs of our colleagues at the Opificio delle Pietre Dure (OPD) in Florence. The UniFI unit of the Department of Physics and Astronomy began developing an X-ray based radiographic/tomographic system specifically tailored to CH applications, in close collaboration with the PNRR CHANGES unit at the Department of Physics and Astronomy of the University of Bologna. The tomograph is going to be based in the new laboratory of nuclear techniques at the OPD conservation centre and will be available for deployment in

museums or conservation sites.

1.3 Scope of WP1 – Advanced Non-invasive Methods

WP1 operates within the strategic framework defined by Spoke 5, emphasizing interdisciplinary collaboration, the creation of synergies across fields of expertise, and the integration of the specific competencies and scientific excellence of each contributing partner. The work package supports innovation on multiple levels—scientific, methodological, and technological—through two main lines of development:

- A. The conceptualization and construction of integrated multimodal diagnostic systems;
- B. The combination of diagnostic techniques with advanced computational and data analysis tools for surface and stratigraphic characterization of cultural heritage materials.

This deliverable presents the methodologies adopted, the systems developed, and the preliminary outcomes of WP1 along these two axes. The work conducted to date represents not only a technical and methodological contribution to the heritage science community, but also a scalable and transferable model for broader application, in line with the CHANGES project's overarching objective of promoting sustainable conservation practices.

The systematic integration of complementary non-invasive techniques within WP1 constitutes a significant advancement in the current state of heritage diagnostics. Continuous research and experimental validation have yielded a deeper understanding of both the capabilities and constraints of individual methods. When combined into multimodal configurations, these techniques have demonstrated enhanced diagnostic

power, allowing researchers to address more complex questions and extract more detailed information than would be possible with single-method approaches.

Several of the selected techniques, such as FTIR, XRF, OCT, and X-ray tomography, have been embedded into cutting-edge platforms, specifically engineered to enhance their diagnostic potential and adaptability to real-world conservation environments. At the same time, WP1 fosters a transition in diagnostic scope from conventional surface-level assessments toward full 3D investigations, enabling a more comprehensive and volumetric understanding of artifact structure and condition.

The approaches developed and summarized in Table 1 illustrate the different combinations of techniques, the institutional partnerships involved, and the respective application areas. These advanced multimodal systems are designed to provide robust, non-invasive analyses capable of revealing key information on material stratigraphy, elemental distributions, and molecular composition critical data for conservation decision-making. Furthermore, their modular and portable nature ensures adaptability to diverse heritage contexts and user requirements.

<i>Techniques (Instruments)</i>	<i>Partners</i>	<i>Applications</i>
CT	Uni FI, Uni BO	Study of small 3D objects (inorganic + organic)
XRF + Cobot	GSSI	Study of 3D objects (inorganic)
IR (MIR) + XRF + Cobot	CNR ISPC CT + SCITEC	Study of 3D painted objects (inorganic + organic)
HSI + OCT	CNR INO	Stratigraphic study of painted objects
PIXE + PIGE + RBS	Uni CT	Quantitative studies
<i>Techniques (protocols)</i>	<i>Partners</i>	<i>Applications</i>
HSI + SORS + statistics	Uni BO + CNR ISPC MI + CNR ISPC CT	Study of multilayered systems
XRF + FTIR + EC	OPD	Study of protective coatings

Table 1 – summary of the advanced methodologies developed in WP1

2. Results

The activity conducted by the research groups within WP1 of Spoke 5 of CHANGES, has yielded the design of the novel instrumentations and integrated multimodal protocols. Each of the techniques explored in is contributing unique insights into the composition, stratigraphy, and structural characteristics of cultural heritage objects. The results already achieved by the WP1 partners with the design of the novel advanced instrumentation demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of combining these non-invasive techniques for comprehensive diagnostics, as summarized below.

2.A Multimodal devices for complex 3D objects

Compact and transportable X-ray CT system (UNI FI):

A compact and transportable X-ray computed tomography (CT) system has been developed at the University of Florence (UNI FI), with the aim of providing high-resolution, non-invasive imaging capabilities specifically tailored to the needs of cultural heritage diagnostics. The system adopts a modular design philosophy, allowing the easy replacement or reconfiguration of its core components, including the X-ray source, detector, and mechanical stages, according to specific analytical requirements. This high level of customizability ensures that the system can adapt to a wide range of diagnostic scenarios, while maintaining portability and operational flexibility for in situ applications. The current setup incorporates a Teledyne DALSA XINEOS 3030HS flat panel detector, chosen for its robustness, compact form factor, and high radiation tolerance [28]. Optimised for the 15–150 keV energy range, the detector offers an active imaging area of $295 \times 295 \text{ mm}^2$ and a spatial resolution of 1952×1952 pixels, with a pixel size of 151.8

μm and a 16-bit image depth. Thanks to its low power consumption (approximately 18 W) the detector does not require forced cooling, enabling thermally stable imaging even in mobile configurations. The use of a columnar CsI scintillator further enhances its sensitivity, while the Gigabit Ethernet interface ensures efficient data transfer.

The X-ray source integrated into the system is a compact and self-shielded Oxford XTF 5011 tube (5000 Series), characterized by a small footprint and low weight (2.6 kg), making it ideal for transportable applications [29]. The tube is encased in a 6 mm thick Pb-bronze housing to eliminate radiation leakage, and a 1 mm layer of Choterm® a thermally conductive and electrically insulating material is placed between the tube and the shielding to improve thermal management and safety. A custom-designed brass component allows for secure cable routing without compromising the shielding integrity. The tube operates within a voltage range of 10–50 kV, with a maximum anode current of 1 mA, and emits a cone beam with a 23° angle. It is equipped with a molybdenum target, a $75 \mu\text{m}$ beryllium exit window, and a focal spot size of approximately $170 \times 70 \mu\text{m}^2$. The thermal stability of the source is maintained by two cooling fans, providing a total airflow of 150 CFM, which ensures that the operating temperature remains below 55°C , thus extending the lifespan of the tube.

To support accurate and repeatable sample positioning during tomographic acquisition, the system includes two high-precision motion stages. The translational stage is based on a linear guide system with recirculating ball bearings and a stepper motor operating via a 1 mm pitch lead screw. Although it operates in open loop and without an encoder, it can achieve a minimum incremental step of $1.25 \mu\text{m}$, allowing for fine control over scanning geometry. Complementing this, the rotational stage is a compact unit (PI-037) equipped with a worm gear mechanism and a low-power (3 W) DC motor [30]. This configuration allows for continuous, bidirectional rotation with angular resolution down

to the microradian level and step sizes as small as $1/1000^\circ$, while supporting loads up to 300 N.

The current system configuration is well-suited for the 3D investigation of small to medium-sized cultural heritage objects, providing volumetric information about internal structures, manufacturing techniques, and degradation phenomena. Thanks to its transportability and modular architecture, the system can be deployed directly at conservation laboratories or heritage sites, eliminating the need to transport fragile artifacts. **Figure 1** illustrates the full assembly of the motion stages and detector in the current prototype configuration.

Figure 1. Assembly of the rotational and translational stages. In the upper part, the detector is visible (the big white cross pointing out its centre).

A distinctive feature of the tomographic system developed at the University of Florence

is its integrated shielding, which enables safe operation outside of dedicated radiographic facilities. This design choice significantly expands the usability of the instrument, particularly in environments such as museums or conservation laboratories, where radiological infrastructure is typically absent and the presence of the public must be taken into account. The shielding structure is primarily composed of 1.5 mm thick brass panels, which provide a first level of containment for scattered radiation. Particular attention was given to the rear side of the system, opposite the X-ray tube and behind the detector, where a higher intensity of backscattered and transmitted radiation is expected. In this critical zone, a graded shielding assembly was introduced, designed to function as a beam stopper. This multilayer structure consists of four sequential materials: a 1 mm layer of PVC, followed by 1.5 mm of aluminium, 1.5 mm of brass, and finally a 1 mm sheet of lead. The graded configuration was specifically chosen to optimize both the attenuation of the X-ray beam and the minimization of secondary radiation effects such as fluorescence or backscatter.

Figure 2. Side view of the tomograph's shielding. It encloses the detector and the motorised stages.

Also visible is the lead glass (shielded for X-ray energies up to 150 kV) used for sample monitoring during analysis.

Radiography and tomography tests demonstrated the system's functionality and helped assess its performance limits and capabilities of the instrument, as shown in Fig. 3 where X-ray images (radiography and tomography reconstruction) of a lamp are presented.

Figure 3. a) Optical image of the lamp, object of the reported radiographic and tomographic analysis; b) lamp radiography; c) lamp tomography, sagittal YZ view.

High-resolution large area mobile CT system (UNI-Bo):

The fast evolving field of X-ray computed tomography and its broad usability make it one of the leading techniques for non-destructive visualization and quantification in many different research fields, including Cultural Heritage. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the demand for on-site X-ray computed tomography (CT) analyses by museums and conservation centers [1-2]. This trend parallels the growing incorporation of the valuable and insightful results provided by this technique into both the restoration process of artworks and the evolving methodologies for the study of

cultural heritage [3].

A well-known limitation of single-energy CT is its reduced capability to discriminate between different materials that exhibit similar grey-scale intensity values, resulting in ambiguities in material identification based solely on attenuation contrast [4]. One of the primary areas of current research in CT imaging is spectral (or multi-energy) imaging, which involves acquiring two or more CT datasets using distinct X-ray energy spectra. Since the X-ray attenuation properties of materials vary as a function of photon energy, this energy-dependent behavior can be exploited to enhance material differentiation beyond the capabilities of conventional CT [5,6].

Several technological approaches to spectral CT exist, with implementations either at the X-ray source level or the detector level. A prominent source-based approach is Dual-Energy Computed Tomography (DECT), wherein two scans of the same object region are acquired using different X-ray energies. These are reconstructed into separate low-energy and high-energy image volumes. Subsequent post-processing—commonly referred to as material decomposition—allows the generation of quantitative maps corresponding to two basis materials. This enables both the classification of constituent materials and the estimation of their relative abundance within heterogeneous structures.

In clinical settings, DECT is routinely employed to generate material-specific density maps, but, more recently, spectral CT techniques have been extended to the field of cultural heritage science, where they are employed not only to correct Beam Hardening (BH) and Metal Artifacts [7] that may appear in the tomographic images of objects consisting of multiple materials with highly differing X-ray interaction properties, but also to characterize complex material compositions in artworks and artifacts. Notable examples

include the identification of the distribution of two red pigments based on lead and mercury in an 18th-century Serbian religious icon [8], and the compositional analysis of ceramic tableware excavated from Pompeii [9].

XRF + 3D morphology cobot system (GSSI):

The Robotic Arm Scan project has been developed to establish a flexible and modular scanning workflow specifically designed for applications in cultural heritage. The system is being developed using the UR10e robotic arm in conjunction with the MoveIt motion planning framework. Significant progress has been achieved on the software side. Core functionalities - including simulated planning [19, 23], collision detection [19], inverse kinematics (IK) [20, 23], and a preliminary user interface (UI) - have been implemented and tested.

This paragraph summarises the activities carried out to date, identifies technical gaps, and presents the next steps for achieving complete system integration, including communication protocols with the scanner and enhanced path planning strategies. Embedded video material accompanies the report to illustrate the current state of development and challenges encountered.

A pilot study was conducted to enable the safe development of a robotic scanning system for artworks. Given their significant cultural and historical value, artworks must be handled with the utmost care and respect. To facilitate automated scanning, a high-precision robotic arm is employed. However, any type of failure—such as configuration errors, software bugs, or parameter misinterpretation—could result in irreversible damage to the artifact. To mitigate these risks, the project incorporates multiple layers of safety

measures. The first measure involves defining a “safe zone” around the artwork, guiding the robotic arm’s permissible workspace. A spherical shape was selected to represent this zone due to its favourable geometric properties, including simplified collision detection and user-friendly configuration requiring only a single parameter. Future phases of the project will introduce additional safeguards to further enhance the reliability and safety of the scanning process

XRF + MIR/SWIR spectroscopy cobot system (CNR ISPC CT + SCITEC):

Analytical approaches in cultural heritage must account for the geometric and material complexity of three-dimensional objects, enabling comprehensive, noninvasive characterization. Three-dimensional artefacts present intrinsic challenges that go beyond those encountered in planar or two-dimensional surfaces. Irregular geometries, including curved or concave areas, protrusions, and fine sculptural details, limit uniform access for spectroscopic probes and can reduce the accuracy of both elemental and molecular measurements. Variations in local curvature, surface orientation, and microtopography directly affect focus distances, signal intensity, and spatial resolution, particularly in optical and infrared spectroscopies, where precise alignment and working distance are critical. Moreover, heterogeneous material composition (such as layered pigments, mixed binders, and composite substrates) induces complex absorption, scattering, and fluorescence phenomena that must be considered to obtain reliable analytical data. Collectively, these factors render conventional flat-sample techniques insufficient for complete characterization of three-dimensional heritage objects, necessitating advanced, adaptive measurement strategies to achieve accurate, reproducible, and high-resolution mapping across the entire surface.

A robotic multimodal spectrometer was developed for noninvasive, in situ analysis of three-dimensional cultural heritage objects. It integrates X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and infrared (IR) spectroscopy in both mid-infrared (MIR) and short-wave infrared (SWIR) ranges, allowing simultaneous elemental and molecular characterization across complex surfaces. The infrared module includes a global silicon carbide (SiC) source, a permanently aligned interferometer, and a thermoelectrically cooled mercury cadmium telluride (MCT) detector, providing spectral coverage from 5000 to 800 cm^{-1} and acquisition speeds up to three times faster than standard commercial instruments. The XRF unit incorporates a low-power X-ray source and a Silicon Drift Detector (SDD), achieving efficient elemental detection in a compact and energy-efficient design. Both modules are mounted on a collaborative anthropomorphic robotic arm with an auxiliary linear stage, enabling precise navigation around large objects up to three meters in size and over intricate surface geometries without contact. The AI-driven control system manages trajectory planning, real-time surface profiling, and adaptive data acquisition, overcoming the constraints imposed by complex forms and heterogeneous materials. While multimodal XRF and MIR/SWIR spectroscopy are well-established for noninvasive imaging of two-dimensional objects, their application to three-dimensional surfaces often yields incomplete results. In infrared spectroscopy, focus distance is critical and difficult to maintain over irregular surfaces, affecting spectral quality and resolution. XRF measurements are less sensitive to working distance but remain influenced by variations in geometry, which impact spatial resolution and detection efficiency. These limitations necessitate a physics-based approach, accounting for geometrical configurations and absorption phenomena, to achieve accurate data. The robotic system is capable of positioning the spectrometer near complex surfaces, maintaining minimum distances around 1 cm, while avoiding physical contact.

The XRF module is complemented by spatial perception through a 3D metrological vision system and collision-avoidance mechanisms, ensuring safe navigation around irregular surfaces. Path planning algorithms utilize a digital twin of the object generated in real time, autonomously optimizing scanning trajectories for multimodal acquisition. The robotic platform operates in a closed loop with AI-based data processing, where geometry perception informs safe positioning, enabling data acquisition and real-time elemental mapping.

Figure 4. Schematic of the XRF cobot system (a) and detail of the designed measuring head (b).

The mockup used for system testing and validation was produced in cartonnage, consisting of paper, glue, and gypsum to form the base support. The painted decorations were realized using a combination of ancient and modern pigments mixed in a gum arabic binder. This configuration reproduces both the material and optical characteristics of historical artifacts, providing a realistic testbed for evaluating the performance of the integrated multimodal spectroscopic platform.

The three-dimensional structure of the mockup was acquired using a laser profilometer,

scanning the object slice by slice. Each slice measured 10 cm in length with a lateral resolution of approximately 10 mm, and overlapping between consecutive slices ensured continuity (**Figure 5a**). Preprocessing involved voxel-based reduction of point clouds and noise filtering, producing a manageable dataset for reconstruction. Poisson surface reconstruction was then applied, including mesh cleaning, bounding box cropping, removal of disconnected clusters via principal component analysis (PCA), and identification of an optimal reference plane using oriented bounding boxes. The trajectory planner generated scanning paths by slicing the reconstructed mesh into lines, concatenated in a serpentine pattern, and adaptively resampled to achieve uniform point density (**Figure 5b**). The tool center point of the robotic arm was aligned with the surface normal, and roll-pitch-yaw angles were derived from the rotation matrix. Collision handling employed enlarged bounding meshes and intelligent rotation strategies based on Rodrigues rotation formulas, combined with translational offsets when necessary (**Figure 5c**). During scanning, the cobot followed the optimized trajectory, acquiring XRF spectra with controlled dwell times. All data were projected back onto the reconstructed mesh for elemental mapping. (**Figure 5d**).

Figure 5. Workflow for 3D acquisition, trajectory planning, and XRF data integration. (a) Laser profilometry; (b) mesh generation serpentine; (c) collision management; (d) 3D XRF mesh for elemental mapping (Mn), and RGB image (Ca, Mn, Pb; Zn, Fe, Mn).

The system enables deconvolution of three-dimensional elemental distributions, accounting for air absorption and solid-phase corrections. Hybrid visualization integrates voxel-based and mesh-based representations. AI-driven diagnostics allow generalization of XRF models across different instruments and materials, multimodal data integration, and advanced fusion of spectral, spatial, and structural information. Self-supervised and transfer learning strategies facilitate analysis of scarce and heterogeneous datasets, enhancing interpretability and robustness of the results. Future developments include full

360° scanning, remote operation with hybrid autonomy, enhanced spatial perception, and collision avoidance. The system supports coordinated XRF and IR acquisition, with adaptive sampling density determined by material heterogeneity. The digital twin is semantically enriched with multimodal datasets, enabling comprehensive mapping, interactive visualization, and long-term data management for cultural heritage studies.

2.B Cutting-edge diagnostics with advanced data processing for stratigraphic studies

Integration of OCT + HSI data for surface/subsurface analysis of paintings

(CNR INO):

The core of the prototype is an SD-OCT (Spectral Domain - Optical Coherence Tomography) device (Ganymede OCT Base Unit at 880 nm, <math><3.0\ \mu\text{m}</math> Resolution, 1.5 to 80 kHz by Thorlabs) with a user-customizable scanner.

The procurement of the initial components has been completed and will be supplemented with additional elements required for the final setup.

For a multi-scale approach, the following lenses were bought: LSM02-BB Scan Lens (Thorlabs, 800 to 1100 nm, EFL = 18 mm, scanning distance 16.1 mm); LSM03-BB Scan Lens (Thorlabs 800 to 1100 nm, EFL = 36 mm); MY10X-823 (Mitutoyo Plan Achromat Objective, 10X, 480 - 1800 nm, 0.26 NA, 30.5 mm WD, resolution 1.3 μm); MY20X-824 (Mitutoyo Plan Achromat Objective, 20X, 480 - 1800 nm, 0.40 NA, 20.0 mm WD, resolution 0.8 μm). Both latter two lenses have 95 mm parfocal length. As the Mitutoyo lenses arrived without the necessary kit to be mounted on the Ganymede OCT device, they haven't been tested yet.

Due to a software bug, it was not possible to perform the calibration of the two Thorlabs lenses as well.

A compact (112.0 mm x 93.8 mm x 41.5 mm) high-resolution (< 2.0 nm) spectrometer (CCT10 by Thorlabs, 200 – 1000 nm wavelength range) was coupled to a round-to-linear fiber bundle and tested on a set of paint samples. A standard bundle was chosen (BFL200HS02 - Round-to-Linear Bundle, 7 x Ø200 µm Core Fibers, High-OH, SMA, 2 m Long) to fit the spectrometer entrance slit (20 µm x 1 mm).

Figure 6. Left) Spectrometer for wavelengths ranging from 200 to 1000 nm; right) round-to-linear fiber bundle

A 45°/0° illumination/detection configuration was employed (see setup in the images below). Measurements were performed on a red sample, following calibration with a 99% reflectance reference standard and a 0% reflectance absorber (dark reference measurement).

Figure 8. Measurement setup used to test the spectrometer performances while measuring left) a colored sample and a white reference standard.

High-resolution large area mobile CT system (UNI-Bo):

Drawing upon the extensive expertise accumulated by our research group over years of activity in the development of digital radiography and three-dimensional computed tomography (CT) acquisition systems, we have designed and implemented a novel high-resolution, large-area, mobile CT system. **Figure 9** illustrates the schematic layout of the experimental setup, highlighting its principal components. Some of these were acquired through funding from the present project, while others were pre-existing assets of the Department of Physics and Astronomy at the University of Bologna (UNI-Bo). The system is equipped with a pair of motorized linear translation stages (Physik Instrumente L-812), each providing a travel range of 610 mm along orthogonal axes. It also integrates a large-area flat-panel detector (Spectrum Logic 2824HR) with an active detection area of $240 \times 280 \text{ mm}^2$. In the current configuration (**Figure 10**), the system offers a total field of view of 850 mm horizontally and 890 mm vertically. The detector features a pixel pitch of $50 \mu\text{m}$, enabling high-resolution CT imaging when required by the specific application. The system is also equipped with a high-precision rotary table and a microfocus X-ray tube.

Figure 9. Scheme of the high-resolution large area mobile CT system developed by UNI-Bo.

Figure 10. Detector and translation axes of the new mobile CT system.

After having set up the mobile system, Dual-Energy Computed Tomography (DECT) tests have been carried out with the objective to investigate the potential of this technique for the

characterization and identification of pigments in painted artifacts. A series of mock-up samples (Figure 11) were prepared using a diverse set of pigments spanning various colors, including Cinnabar, Lead white, Titanium White, Zinc White, Yellow Ocher, Herculaneum Red, Vine Black, Ultramarine Blue, Yellow Naples, and Cadmium Red.

Figure 11. Some of the custom-made mock-ups designed to simulate real painted artworks.

CT scans of these mock-ups were acquired at multiple X-ray energy levels (from 40 kV up to 200 kV with various beam filtration). Following an optimization process aimed at selecting the most effective energy pair for material discrimination, custom material decomposition algorithms were implemented in Python. These algorithms were applied to selected regions of interest (ROIs) within the scanned volumes to generate color-coded compositional maps, enabling the visualization and differentiation of pigments coexisting within the same paint layer (see examples in Figure 12 and 13).

Figure 12. Material decomposition algorithm applied to differentiate Red Herculeum and Cadmium red in DECT images of one of the painted mock-ups: a) map of Cadmium red; b) map of Red Herculeum; c) composite image.

Figure 13. Material decomposition algorithm applied to differentiate cadmium red and cinnabar in DECT images of another painted mock-up: a) map of cinnabar; b) map of cadmium red; c) composite image.

Integration of HSI + SORS + CXRF data through statistics for the non-invasive analysis of paintings (UNI Bo + CNR ISPC MI + CNR ISPC CT):

Several activities were performed by UNI Bo with the aim to propose a protocol based on non-destructive cutting-edge techniques working with different depth of penetration to reconstruct the stratigraphy of a multilayered object without sampling.

- a) A mock-up painting reconstruction named “Sportsmen”, with a complex multilayered structure, was produced and analyzed with the IRIS HSI system, a device by Bruker that combines XRF with VNIR and SWIR reflectance in a whiskbroom scanner. Data were processed fusing XRF and Vis-NIR information by PCA to isolate areas of the paintings according to the different chemical composition. Further, correlations maps and diagrams enabled the identification of each layer in terms of pigments and binder. By inspecting the correlation of the spectral variables between X-ray and reflectance ranges, it was possible to assess whether the identified compounds were applied in the same layers (positive correlation) or were in different layers (negative correlation). The results have been published recently and are the base for further development in combination with other techniques [1]. SORS was separately applied to the painting reconstructions “Sportsmen” and “Young Woman with Unicorn”. Depth-resolved data down to 600 μm from the surface agree and complement the IRIS HSI information. Each processed map agrees with the composition of the areas investigated by IRIS HSI, with the Raman signals of pigment and binder correctly located in each layer. Further implementation will imply: (30) the fusion of the single processed maps to obtain a comprehensive overview of the compounds’ distribution; 31) the addition of OCT and confocal XRF data to the fusion process, to investigate the elemental composition of paint layers at different depth with higher accuracy.
- b) Another dataset was acquired by using the IRIS system on a mock-up titled “Young woman with unicorn”. Data cubes recorded followed a twofold procedure: 1) a copper mask was employed to segment the areas painted with different copper-based pigments. In this way, the mask excluded all the possible interferences coming from other pigments without copper. 2) Near infrared spectra were collected from the masked copper areas and the spectra were used to identify the different copper-

based pigments. The approach demonstrated its validity both for single and multiple layers, with an effective separation between the malachite green pigments used in the composition on a verdigris painting.

- c) To complement the molecular information, a custom-made ERS mapping system operating in the near-infrared (NIR) and mid-infrared (MIR) regions ($5500\text{-}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) was developed. This system integrates an Agilent Cary 630 portable FT-IR spectrometer with a high-precision motorized stage, providing a cost-effective solution while enhancing analytical capabilities and efficiency. The device was tested on a painting reconstruction called "Venus". Currently, the focus is on the noise reduction processes, to balance between data acquisition time and the quality of information. Several denoising methods, such as inverse PCA and wavelet, were tested. Chemometric based multivariate image analysis techniques were conducted on the denoised data to navigate the interpretation of the complex reflectance profiles obtained by the system. Multivariate curve resolution-alternating least squares (MCR-ALS) was carried out for additional depth to the analysis. By decomposing the complex spectral information of the mockup painting into meaningful components, MCR-ALS facilitated a more nuanced understanding of the painting's composition and stratigraphy [32]
- d) The denoising performance was quantitatively assessed using two complementary metrics: the arccosine-based similarity (ACOS) and the derivative-based root mean square error (dRMSE). ACOS quantifies the global similarity in spectral shape between denoised and reference spectra, with values closer to 1 indicating minimal distortion. Conversely, dRMSE captures the effectiveness of noise suppression in the high-frequency domain, as computed on the first derivative of the spectral signals. Lower dRMSE values reflect a better match to the reference in terms of spectral smoothness

and signal clarity [33].

Integration of FTIR + XRF + EC data for the analysis of thin organic coatings on metallic surfaces (OPD):

In the previous phase of our research, we have set a protocol to measure the thickness of organic coatings applied on silver objects of art to protect them against the contact with S-bearing compounds. In the conservation of silver, restorers usually apply synthetic polymers¹, the most popular being Zapon and Paraloid B72, either by brush or by spray, without checking neither the homogeneity or the thickness of the films. The outcome of the research carried out by the OPD in Spoke 5-WP2 demonstrate² that a clear correlation exists between the rate of darkening of the silver surface owing to the contact with sulphur (the so-called tarnishing) and the thickness of the protective, and identified a thickness threshold for each substance tested below which the effectiveness of the protection on the long-term greatly diminishes. Therefore, to get to know the thickness of the coating and its pointwise uniformity is fundamental to set the correct strategy of prevention of tarnishing and to compare the performance of different protective formulation and application methods. Conversely, it is also important to measure the thickness of residual coating films left on the surface after the cleaning steps of the conservation treatment, so as to monitor the effectiveness of the process and to compare different treatments. To achieve that, the OPD in Spoke 5 WP1 developed an integrated protocol, where thickness measurements were carried out non-invasively with methods that can probe different (down to below 1 μm) thickness of the coating, and that are largely spread in conservation science laboratories: X-Ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy (XRF)^{3,4}; Eddy Current testing device (ED) and reflectance FTIR with various instrument

geometries (Figure 14). The various characteristics of each technique were assessed in terms of limitations and advantages of use. After building up the calibration curves for both Paraloid and Zapon on test samples (silver coupons covered with films with known thickness), this approach was applied to two case studies. These are two silver objects of art under conservation in the premises of the Opificio delle Pietre Dure. The first case is a medallion disassembled from an outstanding Medieval reliquary, called "L'albero d'oro" (The golden tree), preserved at the Museo Comunale of Lucignano (Arezzo, Italy), Figure 15 (a and b). The medallion is made of silvered bronze and originally hosted an enamel, now completely lost. The second case study concerns a very ancient and worshipped polychrome wooden sculpture, known as the "Volto Santo di Lucca" (the Holy Face of Lucca), on display in the Cathedral of Lucca (Italy), Figure 16. In particular, this pilot focused on the metallic arch surrounding the sculpture (Fig.3b).

Figure 14: different geometries used for the acquisition of reflectance FTIR spectra with different devices

Figure 15: a) the multi-material reliquary, called *L'albero d'oro*, and b) the detail where the protocol to monitor the cleaning was applied with the measurement areas.

Figure 16: a) the wooden sculpture of the *Volto Santo*, and b) the portion of the metallic arch (called Nimbo) beneath the statue where the application of the coating was monitored in A and B areas.

On the medallion of figure 2 an old coating of Zapon was assessed with reflectance FTIR. The use of XRF and reflectance FTIR allowed to measure the thickness of the Zapon film before (T0 in Table 1) any treatment. A PVA borax gel loaded with a solution 30% acetone in water was applied on each monitored areas for 4 minutes, until no signal of the polymer was detected with FTIR. The thickness of the residual film after each cleaning step was measured with reflectance FTIR with the LUMOS microscope (Table 1).

In the metal (silvered copper) portion of the arch of Figure 3, the presence of a protective film of Paraloid B72 was assessed and a gradual removal of it was monitored in A and B areas. On A, a swab with acetone was used while on B a solvent gel loaded with acetone

was applied for 1 minute. On both areas the treatment was applied in three steps and the thickness of the layer was measured after each step with XRF and reflectance FTIR, Agilent spectrometer geometry 45°/45° (T0, T1, T2, T3 in **Table 2**).

Right hand		Lozenge in the upper part	
T0	3.0±0.4µm	T0	3.1±0.4 µm
T1	2.0±0.4µm	T1	1.1±0.4 µm
T2	0.7±0.4 µm	T2	0.8±0.4 µm
T3	0.7±0.4 µm	T3	No signal
T4	No signal		

Table 1: thickness of the Zapon film on the medallion before (T0) and after each cleaning step in two monitored areas (FTIR band at 840 cm⁻¹ acquired by LUMOS microscope).

A		B	
T0	6.0±0.5µm	T0	9.5±0.5µm
T1	3.8±0.5µm	T1	0.5±0.5µm
T2	3.2±0.5µm	T2	<0.5µm
T3	1.8±0.5µm	T3	<0.5µm

Table 2: thickness of the Paraloid B72 film on the nimbo before (T0) and after each cleaning step for two different methods of cleaning (FTIR band CH stretching at 2965 cm⁻¹)

3. Methodology

The methodologies developed in WP1 are based on an integrative, multimodal approach that combines the strengths of various non-invasive techniques. Each method was selected for its unique analytical capabilities, enabling a comprehensive diagnostic protocol that can be applied in diverse cultural heritage contexts. The following

summarizes the methodologies applied for the development of each multimodal protocol.

3.A Designing multimodal diagnostics for complex 3D objects

Compact and transportable X-ray CT system (UNI Fi):

A transportable X-ray tomograph optimized for Cultural Heritage applications was developed within the framework of the PNRR CHANGES project. The OPD Scientific Laboratory played a crucial role in our project by providing the method and vision of the development, giving constructive feedback and helping define the system's main requirements. Based on their input, we developed a transportable instrument optimized for CH applications, being transportability a feature of utmost importance in the field of Heritage Science. The system offers good spatial resolution and a fully open-source control software. Its portability and integrated safety features make it perfectly suited for in-situ investigations in museums and conservation laboratories.

High-resolution and mobile large area mobile CT system (UNI-Bo):

The mobile CT system operates in X-ray attenuation mode, as most conventional CT systems: an X-ray source emits polychromatic radiation, which is partially attenuated by the object placed in its path, and a digital detector records the transmitted signal. The degree of attenuation is influenced by the material composition and thickness of the object along each ray path. After acquiring a sufficient number of radiographic projections over a range of angles, tomographic reconstruction algorithms are applied to generate two-dimensional cross-sectional images (commonly referred to as slices) or three-dimensional volumetric datasets. These reconstructions enable non-destructive inspection, internal structural analysis, and material classification of the object under investigation. In the reconstructed slices, each pixel corresponds to the average X-

ray attenuation coefficient of the material within the associated voxel.

The imaging of artworks exceeding the dimensions of the detector is carried out using the *tile scanning technique*, whereby the detector is translated across a predefined X-Y grid using motorized stages. At each grid position, a 360-degree CT acquisition is performed by rotating the object, ensuring appropriate overlap between adjacent scanning regions to facilitate subsequent image stitching. Tile scanning can be executed in either step-by-step or “in-fly” acquisition modes. In the first mode, data collection is performed incrementally: the object is rotated stepwise, and multiple frames are averaged at each angular position to enhance image quality, particularly in terms of signal-to-noise ratio. In contrast, in-fly scanning allows for continuous data acquisition, wherein both the rotation of the object and the frame acquisition by the detector occur simultaneously. The angular sampling density can be controlled by adjusting the rotation speed or the detector's frame rate, enabling flexible optimization between image quality and acquisition time depending on the application requirements.

XRF + 3D morphology cobot system (GSSI):

This section provides an overview of the progressive development and integration of key components within the robotic scanning system, focusing on collision object management, path planning, inverse kinematics, user interface enhancements, simulation infrastructure, and ongoing efforts toward path optimization and full hardware integration.

Collision Object Integration: Initial work involved the integration of virtual collision objects into the MoveIt environment to simulate a scanning context. Two objects were introduced: a static table, with hardcoded dimensions and position, and a user-defined spherical volume representing the object to be scanned. These elements guide the planner in generating valid, collision-free trajectories by enforcing spatial constraints. Demonstrations show how removing the table results in unintended collisions with the sphere, highlighting the importance of

contextual geometry during planning ([Video 1](#), [Video 2](#)).

Path Planning and Inverse Kinematics: Subsequent efforts focused on defining scanning poses on the sphere surface. A configurable algorithm was implemented to generate poses around the object at a given height, with the robot's end-effector oriented towards the sphere's centre [34]. This method supports arbitrary numbers of scanning points and proved effective in most scenarios. Nonetheless, some unexpected path behaviours were observed—likely due to Cartesian goal specification or planner local minima. Multiple planners in MoveIt were tested, but none resolved the issue entirely. To improve trajectory reliability, the TRAC-IK inverse kinematics solver [35] was integrated, significantly enhancing planning robustness in Cartesian space. The current algorithm successfully computes and executes up to 20 scanning poses, although minor execution failures remain ([Video](#)). Further improvements are expected by combining joint-space control with Screw Theory, which may offer more optimised scanning paths.

Interface and Visual Tools: A prototype graphical user interface (GUI) was developed using Iridescence, aimed at improving user interaction beyond the constraints of RVIZ. While RVIZ excels at visualising ROS messages for debugging, it is not optimal for end-user configuration. The new GUI enables manipulation of the scanning sphere in 3D space and selection of surface points. It also offers preliminary support for mesh visualisation and rescan selection [36]. Though the current integration is limited, ongoing development aims to streamline real-time interaction ([Demo](#)).

Simulation and Software Infrastructure: A simulation environment was established using Docker and ROS packages to manage the UR10e robotic arm. A GitHub repository was created to maintain the workspace ([Repo 1](#), [Repo 2](#)). Motion control is achieved through a custom MoveIt interface that allows for manual or automated joint command execution [37]. A sphere was initially added to MoveIt as a "no-go" zone to support obstacle-aware motion planning. The sphere's location and radius are user-defined, enabling flexible adaptation to different scanning scenarios.

Pose generation is handled through a custom planner, and inverse kinematics computations are carried out using TRAC-IK.

Path Optimisation and Future Work: Despite positive initial results, some issues with trajectory optimisation persist, particularly in transitions between poses. The investigation into advanced planning strategies is ongoing. Potential solutions include implementing a custom planner in OMPL [38] to constrain movements on the sphere surface or deriving an analytical IK model to maintain end-effector orientation [34].

Additionally, the team is exploring the use of real-time forward kinematics (FK) to track the scanner's position within the robot's reference frame. While the integration with the 3D scanner hardware is pending, the project has already acquired the necessary HW/SW components for UR10 communication, which is expected to simplify the final stages of integration.

XRF + MIR/SWIR spectroscopy cobot system (CNR ISPC CT + SCITEC):

The robotic multimodal spectrometer integrates X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and infrared (IR) spectroscopy, operating across the MIR and SWIR ranges, to enable noninvasive in situ analysis of three-dimensional cultural heritage objects. The system includes an IR module with a silicon carbide (SiC) source, a permanently aligned interferometer, and a thermoelectrically cooled MCT detector, offering spectral coverage from 5000 to 800 cm^{-1} . The XRF unit employs a low-power X-ray source and a Silicon Drift Detector (SDD) for efficient elemental analysis. Both modules are mounted on a collaborative robotic arm with an auxiliary linear stage, ensuring precise, contactless measurements on complex geometries and surfaces up to three meters. Scanning trajectories are generated from a 3D digital twin of the object, with serpentine path planning, adaptive point spacing, and active collision avoidance. Data acquisition is synchronized and managed through an AI-based control system, enabling real-time mapping and multimodal data

fusion. System validation was performed on a full-scale cartonnage mockup of an Egyptian mask, composed of paper, glue, and gypsum, and decorated with ancient and modern pigments mixed in a gum arabic binder.

3.B Combining cutting-edge diagnostics with advanced data processing for stratigraphic studies

Integration of OCT + HSI data for surface/subsurface analysis of paintings (CNR INO):

Feasibility tests were conducted by acquiring the signal from the output port of the Ganimede OCT device, located at the bottom of the beamsplitter module - output port with a removable end cap, item #SM1CP2 - using the Thorlabs spectrometer (see figure below). A 16 mm diameter collimator with an SMA termination was used for signal collection. The obtained signal quality was satisfactory, suggesting that the configuration passing through the two galvo mirrors may be viable.

Figure 17. User-Customizable Scanner with the arrow indicating the entrance port used to couple the spectrometer.

The OCT Ganimede system was deployed but exhibited some unresolved software issues. The Thorlabs visible spectrometer was activated and will be coupled to the OCT device. Procurement procedures for the remaining components required to complete the prototype are currently underway.

Integration of HSI + SORS + CXRF data through statistics for the non-invasive analysis of paintings (UNI Bo + CNR ISPC MI + CNR ISPC CT):

Analyses of the panel "Sportsmen"

- *Description of the painting reconstruction*

The three-layer panel named "Sportsmen" combines classical and traditional paint materials, including various pigments, binders, and varnishes. The ground (first layer) is characterized by gypsum with glue binder. Above the preparation layer, two paint layers were prepared with different pigments and binders. The binder of the second layer is glue, while in the top layer is whole egg.

- *XRF-NIR analysis (IRIS)*

Advanced HSI systems operating in multiple ranges such as visible (400–1100 nm), near infrared (1100–2500 nm) and X-ray (0-48 keV) capturing detailed spectral images. The pixel images collected from the three spectral ranges are spatially aligned to facilitate the combination of the spatial-spectral information. The obtained data were processed with an ad hoc multivariate data strategy including PCA, brushing, correlation maps and diagrams which allow to correlate molecular and elemental variables.

- *SORS mapping*

Micro-Spatially Offset Raman Spectroscopy (SORS) mapping at multiple depths of the sample: the elaboration process of the data is in progress with the aim of fusing the information obtained at the different offset distances.

To improve the interpretability of defocusing micro-SORS data, several pre-processing strategies were tested, including advanced baseline correction, filtering, and normalization techniques. An innovative approach involving the merging of spectral data along the x-axis from different depth layers was also implemented. Spectral unmixing was performed using Multivariate Curve Resolution – Alternating Least Squares (MCR-ALS), which allowed the iterative separation of pure component spectra from overlapping signals. The approach was further refined by arranging data into row-wise augmented matrices along the S (spatial) direction to enhance stratigraphic resolution. Comparative analyses were also designed to evaluate the complementarity between defocused and full micro-SORS configurations, focusing on their respective capacities to extract depth-resolved chemical information. Additionally, Parallel Factor Analysis (PARAFAC) was applied to decompose and visualize multi-component spectral data at different depths.

Analyses of the panel "Young woman with unicorn"

- *Description of the painting reconstruction*

The second multilayer mockup named "Young woman with unicorn" has one paint layer with additional paint details on the sleeves and a varnish layer added on the left-half of the background. It was prepared to study the correlation between elemental information obtained by XRF and molecular information obtained by IR spectroscopy in the SWIR range. The painting was specifically prepared for evaluation of performances of the IRIS instrumentation.

Analyses of the panel "Venus"

- *Description of the painting reconstruction*

The third multilayer mockup named "Venus" has one single paint layer and a varnish layer that covers the left half of the painting. It was prepared to test the potentiality of a custom-made external reflection FT-IR (ER-FT-IR) mapping system, the spectra denoising and spectra data processing new approaches.

A custom-built External Reflection Spectroscopy (ERS) mapping system operating in the near-

infrared (NIR) and mid-infrared (MIR) regions (5500–650 cm^{-1}) was employed. The system combines an Agilent Cary 630 portable FT-IR spectrometer with a high-precision motorized stage. Optimization of denoising strategies for ERS data was carried out using artificially simulated noisy datasets, which enabled the validation and comparison of multiple filtering approaches. Quantitative evaluation was performed using arccosine similarity and derivative-based root mean square error (RMSE) metrics.

Integration of FTIR + XRF + EC data for the analysis of thin organic coatings on metallic surfaces (OPD):

As part of the development of a robust multianalytical protocol for the characterization of organic protective coatings on metal substrates, a combined approach employing FTIR spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and Eddy Current (EC) testing was implemented. The objective was to evaluate and compare the performance of these techniques in measuring the thickness of thin organic films, define their respective feasibility ranges, and determine the most suitable integrated diagnostic setup.

FTIR analyses were conducted in external reflectance mode, utilizing variable angles of incidence to modulate the effective probing depth where smaller angles allow for deeper penetration and larger angles increase surface sensitivity. Different FTIR geometries were employed to evaluate their sensitivity to thin films and their ability to resolve depth-dependent features.

- *Elio* (XGLab), portable XRF spectrometer.
- *Bruker ALPHA*: 25°/25° geometry, spectral range 400–7000 cm^{-1} , resolution 4 cm^{-1} , spot size 4 mm, background collected on gold mirror.
- *Agilent handheld FTIR*: dual geometry setup (45°/45° and 85°/85°), spectral range 650–4000 cm^{-1} , resolution 4 cm^{-1} , 4 mm spot size, background on gold mirror.
- *Bruker LUMOS microscope*: normal incidence (0°/0° geometry), spectral range 700–4000 cm^{-1} , resolution 4 cm^{-1} , measurement area 400 × 400 μm , TC-MCT detector, background on gold mirror.

Software used to process the data: XG lab and PyMca (XRF), EZ Omnic (FTIR). To measure the film thickness calibration curves were built based on the following criteria: for XRF the logarithmic ratio of L3 and K α lines of silver were used, while for reflectance FTIR the CH stretching bands at

Figure 18: calibration curve for XRF for the Paraloid B72 film on a silver substrate

Figure 18: calibration curve for Paraloid B72_ band of C-H stretching (device Agilent FTIR spectrometer)

4. Conclusions

The D1.2 – Technical Report on Design of Multimodal Diagnostics in WP1 of the CHANGES project presents an integrative approach for advanced non-invasive diagnostics in

heritage science. Within this framework, significant progress has been made in developing and applying innovative tools tailored for cultural heritage conservation. One of the key achievements is the development of a novel mobile X-ray computed tomography (CT) system, designed with transportability and usability in mind to meet the specific requirements of conservation professionals. This system, resulting from a collaboration between the UniFI and UniBO teams, addresses a critical gap in Heritage Science tomography instrumentation by offering a large Field of View (850 × 890 mm) combined with high voxel resolution of 15–20 microns. This enables detailed internal imaging of artifacts such as wooden statues, currently among the first objects to benefit from this technology. The system also incorporates a Dual-Energy Computed Tomography (DECT) algorithm for material decomposition, showing promising results in identifying pigments on painted mock-ups. Ongoing work aims to validate these results on real historical artworks, further enhancing the system's diagnostic potential. Through collaboration with the OPD, the tomograph will be made accessible to the broader cultural heritage research community, facilitating widespread adoption. In parallel, WP1 encompasses the advancement of a robotic scanning system integrating X-ray fluorescence (XRF) with 3D morphology analysis, based on the Movelt platform and the UR10e robotic arm from GSSI institute. This system demonstrates robust capabilities such as collision object modelling, precise pose generation, and improved motion stability through the integration of the TRAC-IK inverse kinematics solver. A prototype graphical user interface (GUI) enhances usability by allowing intuitive configuration of scanning parameters, a crucial step toward practical application. While hardware integration is still underway, upcoming phases will focus on refining communication protocols, implementing real-time feedback via forward kinematics, and optimizing scanning

trajectories through advanced mathematical planning techniques. These developments promise to increase the reliability and efficiency of robotic scanning for heritage materials, providing a flexible tool adaptable to diverse conservation scenarios. WP1 includes a multi-analytical protocol combining Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), XRF, and Eddy Current (EC) measurements for the non-invasive analysis of thin organic coatings on metallic surfaces. This protocol, tested on both mock-ups and pilot cases, has demonstrated its effectiveness in monitoring the gradual removal of common protective polymers such as Paraloid B72 and Zapon from silver artifacts. By quantitatively tracking film thinning down to the disappearance of polymer markers, the protocol enables a scientific assessment of cleaning treatments' efficacy, offering conservators a valuable tool for process evaluation and control. This approach highlights WP1's commitment to integrating complementary techniques to achieve detailed, yet non-destructive, insight into material properties and conservation outcomes.

The OCT developed by INO-CNR, Ganimede system was deployed but exhibited some unresolved software issues. The Thorlabs visible spectrometer was activated and will be coupled to the OCT device. Procurement procedures for the remaining components required to complete the prototype are currently underway.

Overall, WP1 of the CHANGES project exemplifies a multidisciplinary approach to heritage diagnostics, combining state-of-the-art imaging, robotic automation, and spectroscopic analysis. The work carried out so far underscores the importance of developing portable, flexible, and reliable diagnostic tools that support in-situ conservation efforts and reduce the risks linked to artifact transportation. By fostering collaboration among research teams and stakeholders, WP1 is laying the foundation for replicable, scalable, and user-friendly methodologies that advance both the science and practice of cultural heritage

preservation.

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